

EVALUATING THE EFFICACY OF HORMONAL THERAPY IN PREMENOPAUSAL PATIENTS WITH HORMONE RECEPTOR-POSITIVE BREAST CANCER

Dr. Mustafa Saad Al-Taie

Consultant Physician, University of Babylon, College of Medicine, Dept. of Oncology

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Abstract

Aim: To highlight Tamoxifen and ovarian suppression as effective adjuvant approaches for premenopausal steroid receptor-positive breast cancer. In addition to encourage surgeons toward breast-conserving surgery with this effective adjuvant approaches.

Patients and Methods: Premenopausal women with early stages, steroid hormone receptor – positive breast cancer, 100 selected patients, for retrospective study were randomly assigned to six or eight cycles of chemotherapy. Followed by two years of monthly Goserelin, and daily Tamoxifen for five years. The primary endpoints were time to recurrence (TTR) for Tamoxifen alone therapy versus combined Tamoxifen and Goserelin therapy.

Results: With two-year follow-up, the combination of Tamoxifen and Goserelin show improved time to recurrence (TTR).

Conclusion: Combination of Tamoxifen and Goserelin improves outcome for premenopausal stage I, II and IIIA, hormone receptor-positive breast cancer.

Keywords: Breast cancer, Tamoxifen, Goserelin

Introduction:

Despite local treatment, up to 50% of women with early-stage breast cancer die of metastatic disease in the absence of adjuvant systemic therapy. Older trials conducted several decades ago suggested that ovarian ablation by surgery or radiation could reduce the risk of recurrence in premenopausal women younger than 50 years. Furthermore, individual trials of adjuvant chemotherapy demonstrated improved recurrence-free and overall survival for premenopausal women with node-positive breast cancer. In 1985, the results from these initial trials were first combined in a meta-analysis of all randomized trials of adjuvant ovarian ablation or chemotherapy. This analysis unequivocally demonstrated the benefit of adjuvant chemotherapy in premenopausal women with node-positive breast cancer. This combined analysis also demonstrated improved outcome for younger women treated with ovarian ablation. Finally, in other studies, the equivalence of oophorectomy and chemical ovarian suppression by chronic administration of luteinizing hormone-releasing hormone agonists for treatment of premenopausal women with steroid receptor-positive metastatic breast cancer was demonstrated. (1)

Premenopausal status was defined by any one of the following; less than 4 months since last menstrual period, 4 to 12 months since last menstrual period with premenopausal FSH level, or less than 61 years of age with a previous ovary-sparing hysterectomy and premenopausal FSH level (2). Hormones play an important role in the development and progression of breast cancer. Estrogen and its metabolite and other steroid hormone like progesterone all have been shown to have an effect. breast cancer risk is related to estrogen exposure

over time. Patients with hormone receptor- positive tumors survive (2-3 times longer than patients with hormonal receptor- negative tumors (3). Patients with tumor negative for both estrogen and progesterone receptor are not considered candidate for hormonal therapy. Tumor positive for both receptor have higher response rate (>50%) to endocrine therapy than those not expressed estrogen and progesterone receptor (<10%). Tumor positive for one receptor but not the other has an intermediate response rate of 33%. The determination of estrogen and progesterone receptor status used to require biochemical evaluation of fresh tumor tissue. Hormone receptor status should be ascertained for both premenopausal and postmenopausal patient to identify patients who are most likely to benefit from endocrine therapy. Hormones receptors are detectable in more than 90%of well differentiated ductal and lobular invasive breast cancer (3). Positive ER and PR were defined as (10 fm/mg) protein by biochemical assay or positive immunohistochemistry according to individual laboratory standards (4, 5).

Hormonal Therapy; Tamoxifen (Nolvadex®), is a competitive antagonist of the estrogen receptor in breast tissue via its active metabolite, Hydroxytamoxifen. Tamoxifen causes cells to remain in the G₀ and G₁ phases of the cell cycle. Because it prevents (pre)cancerous cells from dividing but does not cause cell death, tamoxifen is cytostatic rather than cytotoxic. In other tissues such as the endometrium, it behaves as an agonist, and thus may be characterized as a mixed agonist/antagonist. Tamoxifen is the usual endocrine (anti-estrogen) therapy for hormone receptor-positive breast cancer in pre-menopausal women, and is also a standard in post-menopausal women although aromatase inhibitors are also frequently used in that setting (6). Goserelin (Zoladex®) (6); is a synthetic analogue of a naturally occurring luteinizing-hormone releasing hormone (LHRH). It rapidly binds to the LHRH receptor cells in the pituitary gland thus leading to an initial increase in production of luteinizing hormone and thus leading to an initial increase in the production of corresponding sex hormones. Eventually, after a period of about 14–21 days, production of LH is greatly reduced due to receptor down regulation, and sex hormones are generally reduced to castrate levels. This drug is given as (1to3) monthly subcutaneous injection.

Patients and methods; this is a retrospective study implicating premenopausal women with operable invasive stage I, II and IIIA, estrogen and/or progesterone receptor (ER and/or PR) positive breast cancer. Involving no, one or more axillary lymph nodes by conventional histology were eligible for the study. For the period from January 2010 to January 2012,

100 patients in Marjan teaching hospital, oncology unit, in Al Hilla Province, were enrolled. The staging of breast cancer is as in table (1).

Table (1): staging of breast cancer

Stage	T	N	M
Stage 0	Tis	N 0	M 0
Stage I	T 1	N 0	M 0
Stage IIA	T 0	N 1	M 0
	T 1	N 1	M 0
	T 2	N 0	M 0
Stage IIB	T 2	N 1	M 0
	T 3	N 0	M 0

Stage IIIA	T 0	N 2	M 0
	T 1a	N 2	M 0
	T 2	N 2	M 0
	T 3	N 1	M 0
	T 3	N 2	M 0
Stage IIIB	T 4	N 0	M 0
	T 4	N 1	M 0
	T 4	N 2	M 0
Stage IIIC	Any T	N 3	M 0
Stage IV	Any T	Any N	M 1

All patients received appropriate local therapy with modified radical mastectomy and underwent axillary dissection. Women were excluded if they had bilateral breast malignancies, locally advanced breast cancer, pregnant, lactating, or metastases. Staging before random assignment included normal chest x-ray, abdominal ultrasound and blood studies for hematologic, hepatic and renal function. After stratification by number of positive axillary lymph nodes (1 to 3 or 4 to 9), hormone receptor status (ER+/PR+, ER+/PR-, ER-/PR+), and time since primary surgery (6 weeks), patients were assigned to receive (6 or 8) cycle chemotherapy, followed by Goserelin and Tamoxifen. . Patients assigned to receive Goserelin, received a 3.6 mg depot subcutaneously every 4 weeks for 5 years beginning on cycle 6 or 8, day 29 of chemotherapy. Patients randomly assigned to receive Goserelin plus Tamoxifen also took Tamoxifen 10mg PO/ bid for 5 years beginning on cycle 6 or 8, day 29 of chemotherapy. **Statistical terms; Time To Recurrence (TTR);** is defined as time from random assignment to disease recurrence or new breast cancer primary, where death without recurrence was censored(7).

Disease-Free Survival (DFS); is defined as time from random assignment to disease recurrence, new breast cancer primary, or death, whichever occurred first(7). **Overall Survival (OS)(7);** is defined as time from random assignment to death.

Hazard ratio (HR); Measure of how often a particular event happens in one group, compared to how often it happens in another group, over time. A hazard ratio of one means that there is no difference in survival between the two groups. A hazard ratio greater than one or less than one means that survival was better in one of the groups(8).

RESULTS:

Patient Selection and Characteristics; Between Jan. 2010 and Jan. 2012,100 patients were selected. The patient’s characteristics were distributed according to the following tables:

Table (2): Demographic distribution.

	Number of patients
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Age <40	39
>40 years	61
Marital status Married	87
unmarried	13
Parity status Para	81
Null Para	6

Table (3): General characteristics of tumors

		Number of patients
No. of LN	N0(0)	38
	N1(1-3)	40
	N2(4-9)	22
Tumor size	T1(<2cm)	30
	T2(2-5cm)	70
Stages:		
	Stage I	14
	Stage II	64
	Stage IIIA	22
Receptor status:		90
	ER+/PR+	
	ER-/PR+	7
	ER-/PR-	3

Patient’s characteristics were assigned across treatment groups (Table 4).

Table (4): characteristics of selected patients.

Patients characteristics	No. of Patients on Tamoxifen		No. of patients on Tamoxifen + Goserelin		Total number of patients	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
No. of nodes N0(0)	25	37	13	38	38	38
N1(1-3)	27	40	13	38	40	40
N2(4-9)	14	21	8	23	22	22
Age=<40	18	27	21	61	39	39
>40	48	72	13	38	61	61
ER/PR Status	57	86	33	97	90	90
ER+/PR+						

ER-/PR+	6	9	1	27	7
ER+/PR-	3	4	0	03	3
Tumor size(cm)T1(<2)	17	25	13	38	30
T2(2-5)	49	74	21	61	70
Total	66	34			100

Outcomes; With a follow-up for recurrence- free period of 6 months (as a minimum) to 24 months (as a maximum) of patients still alive on January, 2012 there have been 5 recurrences, no significant events and no deaths. Because there is no deaths in this presented study, DFS and OS have excluded statistically from the outcome due to lack of comparison. Sites of and times to recurrence in relation to patient characteristics are shown in Table 5.

The use of combination of Tamoxifen and Goserelin will significantly improve TTR, when compared with Tamoxifen alone treatment, especially when hazard ratio was adjusted for age, nodal status, ER/PR status, and tumor size. Table 6.

Table (5): Sites × of recurrence and patients characteristics

No. of patient	Site(s)	Age (years)	Stage	Grade	ER/PR Status	Tamoxifen alone	Tamoxifen + Goserelin	TT R /mo n
1	Local+liver	25	T2N0	2	ER+/PR-	Yes	No	6
1	Lt.pleural effusion	37	T2N2	1	ER+/PR+	Yes	No	12
1	Rt. pleural effusion	46	T2N2	2	ER+/PR+	Yes	No	12
1	Ipsilateral axillary and supraclavicular LN	43	T2N1	2	ER+/PR+	Yes	No	8
1	Local	43	T2N2	2	ER+/PR+	Yes	Yes	6

Table (6): Treatment effect and patient characteristics

Patient characteristics	Tamoxifen + Goserelin vs.Tamoxifen	
	HR	CI
Age<40TTR	*	0
Age>40TTR	1.85	(0.85- 3.99)
NodesN0TTR	*	0
N1TTR	*	0
N2TTR	0.88	(0.105- 7.308)
ER/PR Status ER+/PR+TTR	0.58	(0.199- 5.014)
ER-/PR+TTR	**	
ER+/PR-TTR	***	
Tumor sizeT1TTR	**	

T2TTR	0.58	(0.07_4.77)
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*No recurrence at Tamoxifen–Goserelin group (combined treatment is the best).

**No recurrence in both treatment groups.

***For patients with ER+/PR-, there is no patient took the Tamoxifen-Goserelin treatment (no number). The landmarks (*, **) mean HR for TTR cannot be adjusted for patient characteristics; however, TTR is significantly improved with combined treatment.

limitations; Unfortunately, this study lacks the real and accurate statistics about the patient compliance and side effects of treatment because of the difference and irregularity in time and places of patient attendance and lack of documentation, especially with Tamoxifen which is given as an outpatient treatment. However, in general, the compliance was accepted and there were no serious adverse effects of treatment.

Discussion; The role of the hormonal therapy is evaluated through a randomly assigned study of Tamoxifen alone and combined Tamoxifen –Goserelin treatment in premenopausal women with stage I,II and IIIA, steroid hormone receptor-positive breast cancer.

The results obtained from this study showed that combined Tamoxifen- Goserelin therapy significantly improved TTR when compared with Tamoxifen therapy alone, especially in women less than 40 years, while those more than 40 years show no benefit from the addition of Goserelin. Similar results were obtained from Davidson et al(7), where addition of combined Tamoxifen-Goserelin therapy following full course of chemotherapy will significantly improve outcome (hazard ratio for TTR=0.75 for those patient less than 40 years and hazard ratio for TTR=1 for those more than 40 years). Therefore, the selection of premenopausal women was the major strength of this study as those patients are most likely to get benefit from this treatment modality. The selection was restricted to the patients with steroid hormone receptor positive tumors as they are most likely to benefit from the hormonal therapy. This is supported by results of trial of Bardou V, Arpino G. et al.(5), where patients with ER+ve / PR+ve breast cancer had great benefit from adjuvant endocrine therapy (hazard ratio for TTR =0.78). In our current study, there is one of five recurrences, which is ER+ve / PR-ve disease on Tamoxifen only therapy, which heralded the prognostic significance of progesterone receptors as this is shown by trial of Fernoet al studies involving patients with ER+/PR+ breast cancer which show significant improvement with Tamoxifen therapy for 5 years, compared with those have ER+/PR- tumor.

Further, all patients randomly assigned for axillary lymph nodes status; whether they are negative (N0), or positive (N1 or N2), a subset group of patients has higher recurrence rate show significant improvement in TTR. By comparing with trial of Davidson et al(7) study showed no difference in improvement of TTR for patients with N0 disease given Tamoxifen alone treatment (HHR= 1), while patients with N1 and N2 disease given Tamoxifen alone showed no improvement in TTR (HR=1.57 , 3.52 respectively). In this trial, patients with T1 disease show good improvement regarding TTR for both modalities; but there is significant in TTR with combined treatment (HR=0.58) for patients with T2 disease. Bardou V., Arpino G. et al trial (1) showed no difference in TTR in patients with T1 disease given Tamoxifen alone treatment (HR=1), and also those with T2 disease given Tamoxifen alone treatment showed no improvement in TTR (HR=1.29).

Tamoxifen and Goserelin were used for 5 years and 2 year respectively and were given after completion of chemotherapy, a strategy that seems to be optimal based on oncological guidelines (6).

Major drawbacks of this presented study are; Lack of real and accurate statistics concerning patient's compliance and side effects of treatment. However, Patients compliance was accepted and no serious complications of treatment were documented. And short duration of the follow up, and the treatment strategy is 5 years, so the duration of the follow up should be

longer in order to perform a better evaluation of the hormonal therapy in term of improve TTR.DFS &OS. And pick up more serious side effect and toxicities of treatment modality.

3. Both treatment groups are not equal, however statistically the results can be compared between them.

Conclusion:

1. Combined Tamoxifen-Goserelin treatment is significantly effective for a patient less than forty years, but it is not for the ages more than forty years.
2. Breast cancers of ER+/PR+ status are highly responsive to Tamoxifen- Goserelin treatment.
3. Patients with N0, N1 and N2, and those with T1 and T2 breast cancer are a good candidate for receiving combined Tamoxifen –Goserelin treatment.

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